

PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract

This paper aims to teach English language with pedagogical methods.

Keywords: pedagogical approaches, technologies, EFL classroom, pupils.

Introduction

There are a lot of changes in the field of education today. Education, of course, is the basis for growth. There is a growing interest in English in particular. In the process of teaching English, which is becoming one of today's requirements, the possibilities are endless. There are conditions for each of us to master this language. One of the priority tasks of the President is to take measures to improve the English language. Therefore, the decrees "On measures to further improve the system of foreign language teaching" were adopted. In the law: "Development of innovative methods of teaching foreign languages at the Uzbek State University of World Languages consists of 34 state units of the Republican Scientific-Practical Center, 39 state units of the Ministry of Public Education and the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education. to be accepted for information. Establish a procedure according to which the Agency: coordinates the activities of state bodies and organizations, local executive authorities and public educational institutions in the promotion of foreign language teaching; develops and implements methodologies in collaboration with ministries and agencies that allow civil servants to conduct their professional activities in foreign languages; identifies comprehensive measures to promote the study of at least ten high-demand foreign languages; develops qualification requirements and assessment criteria for foreign language teachers and organizes the process of awarding them a qualification category on the basis of openness;

On termination of the Republican Scientific-Practical Center for the Development of Innovative Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages under the Uzbek State University of World Languages of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter - the Center) to approve the proposal. To determine: Development and continuous

improvement of the state educational standards, curricula and programs, educational and methodical manuals according to the international standards on foreign languages for the whole system of continuous education of the Center of the Agency is the legal successor of contracts, rights and obligations under economic contracts. As we can see, the strength of the focus on the English language, the growing conditions created in it, is focused only on our education. English is an international language. If we master this language deeply, the door of great opportunities will open before us. Our country will prosper, our life will improve, opportunities and development will increase. Currently, developments are creating the basis for teachers to teach English using modern innovative pedagogical technologies. Teachers get more results through such updates.

Prevents students from getting bored, motivates them, ensures that the lessons are answered now. They learn more and receive more information. Delivering all information resources to students through interesting, popular changes in the classroom is a modern requirement, a requirement of the time. Because changes and updates expand the student's worldview and aesthetics. Now the student simply cannot listen to the lessons. We need to engage them with something interesting and inform them. Then the student can listen to us and make additions. The advantage of such technologies is that they are important for 100% involvement of the student in the lesson. Only with these technologies can the teacher satisfy the different needs of the student in line with each epoch.

In the past, learning and education simply meant face-to-face lectures, reading books or printed handouts, taking notes and completing assignments generally in the form of answering questions or writing essays. In short; education, learning and teaching were considered impossible without a teacher, books and chalkboards. Today, education and training have taken on a whole new meaning. Computers are an essential part of every classroom and teachers are using DVDs, CD-ROMs and videos to show pupils how things work and operate. Pupils can interact with the subject matters through the use of such web based tools and CD-ROMs. Moreover, each pupil can progress at his/her own pace.

Technology allows distance learning: Perhaps the greatest impact of technology in the field of learning is its ability to help several people learn simultaneously from different locations. Learners are not required to gather at a predetermined time or place in order to learn and receive instructions and information. All one needs is a computer connected to a modem (or with a CD drive); these tools can literally deliver a 'classroom' in the homes and offices of people. Technology allows group Learning: There are naysayers who argue that distance learning of this sort cannot help pupils receive the support of traditional group-based

learning. For proving this theory wrong, technology has helped provide distance learners with online communities, live chat rooms and bulletin boards. All these allow pupils to collaborate and communicate even though they are isolated in their own space.

Technology allows individual pacing: Multimedia tools, on-line and CD-ROM based training have helped eliminate the need for an instructor-based lesson plans. Pupils who grasp concepts faster proceed and move along, without being held back by ones who need more time and help for learning. Such individual pacing is beneficial to all. Technology helps lower training costs and increases productivity: Another benefit of using technology to reach many pupils in shorter time is lowering training costs. Corporate and academic Institutions can reduce their costs of delivering lessons to pupils on a per-pupil basis. Moreover, technology produces quantifiable results and allows pupils to put into practice this information quickly and with better results. Through the use of technology, pupils can considerably save time and increase their productivity. Both these points justify the higher costs of advanced technological tools. Roadblocks in the use of technology in learning: Naturally, for education technology to have a positive impact on pupils, it should be designed and prepared well. Tools used for disseminating information must be developed with pupils in mind. There are also factors like lack of computer/technology literacy to be considered. Schools and businesses must bear in mind that education technology is simply a tool and its success depends largely on the amount of planning that goes into it. Using education technology can be a right choice as long as all such factors are considered.

The goal of our teaching is to develop individuals who value knowledge, learning and the creative process, who can and will think for themselves, recognize the limits of individual reflection and build upon mutual understandings of social situations. Critical thinking is the intellectually disciplined process of actively and skillfully conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and/or evaluating information gathered from, or generated by, observation, experience, reflection, reasoning, or communication, as a guide to belief and action. It is based on universal intellectual values: clarity, accuracy, precision, consistency, relevance, sound evidence, good reasons, depth, breadth, and fairness. There are many techniques and methodologies as how one can stimulate creative and critical thinking and it should be mentioned that most techniques or methodologies facilitate the breaking down of a situation into specific parts and following a repeatable process. Five techniques you can use in

the creative thinking process are: lateral thinking, metaphoric thinking, positive thinking, association triggering, capturing and interpreting dreams.

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